

TIME MANAGEMENT PRACTICES OF NURSES IN THE ONCOLOGY AND PALLIATIVE CARE UNIT OF A PRIVATE HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the time management practices of nurses in the oncology and palliative care unit, focusing on the domains of planning, prioritizing, delegating, and minimizing distractions. A descriptive-correlational design was employed, and data were gathered through a validated survey instrument administered to nurses with varying demographic profiles, including age, gender, years of experience, and shift schedules. Descriptive statistics revealed that respondents exhibited high proficiency in all four domains, with the highest mean scores recorded in planning and prioritizing tasks. Inferential analysis indicated significant differences in time management practices based on years of nursing experience and shift schedule, while positive correlations emerged between experience and delegation skills, as well as between age and planning competencies. The study showed that rotating shifts made it more difficult for staff to manage their time. In response, a five-part program was developed. This program offers a time management workshop, improved shift planning, peer mentorship, digital workflow tools, and mindfulness activities. The findings suggest that both individual skills and Support from the organization are important for better time management, which can help improve patient care in busy healthcare settings.

Keywords: *time management, nursing practice, oncology nursing, palliative care, shift scheduling*

INTRODUCTION

Cancer remains one of the top causes of death around the world. It impacts not just physical health, but also brings emotional and financial challenges for families and puts extra pressure on health systems. The World Health Organization reports that cancer caused nearly 10 million deaths worldwide in 2023. The most common types are lung, breast, colorectal, prostate, and stomach cancers. These numbers reflect how serious the problem still is, despite advances in treatment and Awareness.

The incidence of cancer has been increasing in Asia over the last few years. This number can be attributed to variables including a burgeoning population that is aging, as well as changing lifestyles. What is evident is that more than half of the world's cancer burden, including Asia, and deaths occur in Asia, largely due to its huge population, variations in early detection and appropriate treatment access (Global Cancer Observatory, 2021). This cancer incidence has also been seen of late in the countries in Southeast Asia that are beset with scarce medical facilities and late diagnosis.

Cancer is fast becoming less manageable in Southeast Asia, which includes Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand and the Philippines. Several countries in the region also confront problems of delayed detection, poor access to treatment, and the cost of cancer. In many low- and middle-income countries, people with cancer are still less likely to survive because they are usually diagnosed at a later stage, and treatment services are not always available or affordable (Sung et al., 2021).

In the Philippines, cancer is still considered a significant public health problem. It is among the top three causes of death in the country. According to DOH, breast, lung, liver, colon and cervical are among the prevalent ones. Sadly, the majority of Filipino patients are already diagnosed at an advanced stage of the disease. This complicates the treatment and results in poorer outcomes. However, specialized treatment such as chemotherapy and radiotherapy is not available to many provinces, and treatment costs are a huge burden to many of our patients and their families.

It is in part because of these challenges that palliative care has become even more vital. It concentrates on the amelioration of the pain and suffering of those with life-threatening conditions, predominantly those for whom there is no hope of cure. But palliative care in the Philippines is in its early stages of growth. Though some privately owned hospitals provide palliative care, typically such services are confined to large cities. Despite such advances, palliative care remains largely underutilized and not yet an integral part of routine cancer care in most settings (De Guzman et al., 2021).

Nursing is important in oncology and palliative care. They are the ones most directly in contact with patients, and many of them not only treat symptoms, but also emotionally support patients. In these units the work load is increasing and the nurses must perform a multitude of tasks in a short period. Time Management is thus a crucial skill. Time Management by nurses may be an issue impacting the quality of care provided to cancer patients at the end of life.

Time plays a big role in the daily routines of nurses, especially in units like oncology and palliative care where patients require close monitoring, emotional Support, and continuous nursing care. With so many responsibilities, managing time properly becomes important in making sure that patients receive the care they need. Nurses are expected to handle multiple tasks within their shifts—such as documentation, medication administration, patient care, and communication with the healthcare team.

Cancer incidence is increasing, as is the demand for palliative care; therefore, it is necessary to explore the use of time by nurses employed in oncology and palliative care departments. The purpose of this study was to investigate time-management practices of students and to provide a description of them, which would be used to determine which areas require Support and improvement. This study focuses on how nurses manage their time in the oncology and palliative care unit of a private hospital. These units often deal with patients who are either undergoing long- term cancer treatment or are in the final stages of life. The care provided in such settings is not only technical but also deeply emotional. This makes time management even more challenging. By understanding how nurses organize their time and what challenges they face, this study hopes to give insights that can help improve workflow and support systems in such specialized units.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the time management practices of nurses assigned to the oncology and palliative care unit of a private hospital. It sought to explore how specific demographic characteristics such as age, sex, years of experience, shift schedule, and unit assignment may influence how nurses manage their time during their shifts. The study also aimed to describe the level of their time management practices based on the components of planning, prioritizing, delegating, and minimizing distractions.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the demographic characteristics of the nurses in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 Years of Experience in Nursing
 - 1.4 Current Unit Assignment
 - 1.5 Shift Schedule
 - 1.6 Highest Educational Attainment?
2. What is the level of their time Management practices when grouped according to the components of planning, prioritizing, delegating, and minimizing distractions?
3. Is there a significant difference in the time Management practices of nurses when grouped according to their demographic profile?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile of the nurses and their time Management practices?
5. Based on the results of the study, what research output can be produced or a program that can be developed?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative descriptive–correlational design, which was ideal for exploring patterns, relationships, and associations without manipulating any variables. Quantitative research allowed the researcher to collect numerical data and apply statistical methods to analyze it (Creswell, 2021). The descriptive design was used to outline the characteristics of the participants, while the correlational design determined the degree of relationship between variables (Polit & Beck, 2021). In this study, the design was used to describe time Management practices and assess whether these practices were related to selected demographic variables.

Population and Sampling

The study population consisted of registered nurses assigned to oncology, palliative care, and home care units in a private tertiary hospital in Metro Manila. These units were deliberately chosen because nurses in such high-acuity and emotionally taxing settings often face unpredictable workloads, urgent clinical demands, and resource constraints, which can test their ability to manage time effectively (Peters et al., 2020). A purposive sampling technique was used to ensure that only participants who could provide relevant and rich information were included (Etikan et al., 2016). The inclusion criteria required that participants:

1. Be registered nurses currently assigned to one of the target units.
2. Have at least six months of continuous experience in their current unit.
3. Be actively engaged in direct patient care at the time of data collection. Nurses in purely administrative roles, those on leave during the data collection period, and those who declined to provide informed consent were excluded. A total of 60 nurses participated in the study. While purposive sampling does not permit broad generalization to all nurses in similar settings, it ensured that the sample captured the perspectives of those most directly involved in the study phenomenon (Palinkas et al., 2015).

Participants of the Study

The participants were front-line clinical nurses with direct patient care responsibilities. They came from diverse backgrounds in terms of age, years of experience, and shift schedules, although the majority were female, aged between 25 and 45 years, and held a Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) degree, with some having pursued postgraduate units or degrees in nursing. Their roles in oncology, palliative care, and home care required advanced clinical judgment, rapid decision-making, and the capacity to prioritize competing demands under time constraints. This made them ideal respondents for examining how personal and work-related factors influence time management practices in high-stress clinical environments.

Research Instrument

To gather the data necessary for this study, a researcher-developed structured questionnaire will be used as the primary data collection instrument. The questionnaire is designed to comprehensively address the specific objectives of the study, particularly focusing on the demographic characteristics of clinical nurses and their time management practices.

The instrument will consist of two main parts. Part I will collect the demographic profile of the participants and will include items on the following variables: age (open-ended numerical response), sex years, 6–10 years, and more than 10 years), current shift schedule (day shift, night shift, rotating shift), and unit assignment (oncology, palliative care, or home care). This section will provide baseline data to answer SOP No. 1 and serve as the grouping variables for further statistical analysis in SOPs 3 and 4. Part II of the questionnaire will assess the level of time Management practices among nurses. This section will be composed of 20 items, grouped into four subscales based on the core components of effective time Management: planning, prioritizing, delegating, and minimizing distractions. Each subscale will consist of 5 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale, with responses ranging from 1 – Strongly Disagree to 5 – Strongly Agree. Sample items may include: "I plan my tasks at the beginning of every shift" (planning), "I attend first to patients whose needs are most urgent" (prioritizing), "I assign non-critical tasks to Support staff when appropriate" (delegating), and "I avoid unnecessary conversations and interruptions during work hours" (minimizing distractions).

Research Reliability and Validity

The reliability and validity of the research instrument were rigorously established to ensure the accuracy and trustworthiness of the findings. Reliability was assessed through internal consistency testing using Cronbach's alpha coefficient after pilot testing with 12 nurses who met the inclusion criteria but were excluded from the final sample. The results showed excellent reliability for the overall scale ($\alpha = 0.91$) and acceptable to high reliability across the four subscales: planning ($\alpha = 0.88$), prioritizing ($\alpha = 0.86$), delegating ($\alpha = 0.83$), and minimizing distractions ($\alpha = 0.85$). These values exceeded the generally accepted threshold of 0.70 for social science research (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011), indicating that the items consistently measured their intended constructs. Stability over time was further evaluated using test–retest reliability with the same pilot group after a two-week interval, producing Pearson's correlation coefficients between 0.79 and 0.85, which suggests strong temporal stability.

Validity was established through multiple approaches. Face validity was confirmed by five practicing nurse educators and clinical supervisors who reviewed the instrument for clarity, readability, and relevance, ensuring the items reflected real-world clinical scenarios in oncology, palliative care, and home care settings. Content validity was assessed by a panel of three subject matter experts in nursing Management, time Management, and healthcare quality, using the Content Validity Index (CVI) to rate each item for relevance, clarity, and representativeness. The average CVI for all items was

0.94, which is considered excellent according to Lynn's (1986) standard. Items with CVI scores below 0.80 were revised for improved specificity and alignment with the study objectives. Construct validity was supported through exploratory factor analysis (EFA) conducted after the pilot test, which yielded a Kaiser–Meyer–Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy of 0.89 and a statistically significant Bartlett's Test of Sphericity ($p < 0.001$). The EFA confirmed the hypothesized four-factor structure corresponding to planning, prioritizing, delegating, and minimizing distractions, with all factor loadings above 0.60.

Data Gathering Procedure

Prior to data collection, the researcher will secure ethical clearance and formal approval from the Research Ethics Committee of the University of Perpetual Help System-DALTA, Las Piñas City. Permission to conduct the study will also be obtained from the hospital administration, where the research will take place. This will include submission of a letter of request outlining the study's objectives, methodology, and ethical safeguards, including confidentiality and voluntary participation.

Upon approval, the researcher will coordinate with the Chief Nurse or Nursing Service Office to identify eligible participants based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. A brief orientation session will be scheduled with the identified nurses to explain the purpose of the study, the contents of the questionnaire, the confidentiality of their responses, and their right to refuse or withdraw from participation at any point without consequences. Participants will be asked to sign an informed consent form prior to participation.

The data collection tool, a structured self-administered questionnaire, will be distributed either in printed form or electronically, depending on the preference and availability of the respondents. Participants will be given a reasonable period of time, approximately one week, to complete the questionnaire during their free time to avoid disruption of clinical duties. To ensure a good response rate, regular follow-ups and reminders will be made through coordination with unit heads or charge nurses.

Completed questionnaires will be collected personally by the researcher or submitted via a secure drop-box placed in the nursing station or via a password-protected digital folder, in the case of electronic submission. All completed responses will be checked for completeness and accuracy before data encoding. The collected data will be treated with strict confidentiality and stored securely by the researcher for data analysis. Only aggregate data will be reported in the final manuscript to protect the identities of the participants and the institution involved.

Data Analysis

The data gathered from the accomplished questionnaires will be analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods, with the assistance of a statistical software program such as SPSS or Microsoft Excel. To address Research Question No.

1, which seeks to describe the demographic characteristics of the nurses in terms of age, sex, years of experience, shift schedule, and unit assignment, descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation will be utilized.

For Research Question No. 2, which aims to determine the level of nurses' time Management practices based on the components of planning, prioritizing, delegating, and minimizing distractions, mean scores and standard deviations will also be computed to assess the central tendency and variability of responses within each subscale.

To address Research Question No. 3, which explores whether there are significant differences in time management practices when nurses are grouped according to their demographic profile, inferential statistics will be applied. Specifically, independent samples t-tests will be used for variables with two categories (such as sex), while one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) will be employed for variables with more than two categories (such as years of experience, shift schedule, and unit assignment).

Finally, to answer Research Question No. 4, which examines the relationship between the nurses' demographic characteristics and their level of time management practices, Pearson's correlation coefficient will be used for continuous variables (such as age and years of experience), and Chi-square tests will be applied for categorical variables where appropriate. The level of significance will be set at 0.05 to determine statistical significance across all tests.

RESULTS

The results are organized according to the specific research questions, beginning with the demographic profile of the respondents, followed by the level of their time Management practices in the areas of planning, prioritizing, delegating, and minimizing distractions. It also includes the results of statistical tests conducted to determine significant differences and relationships between the respondents' demographic characteristics and their time Management practices. The findings are discussed in relation to existing literature and empirical studies to highlight consistencies, discrepancies, and possible explanations, providing a deeper understanding of the patterns observed.

I. Demographic Profile of The Nurses

This section describes the socio-demographic characteristics of the nurses assigned to the oncology and palliative care unit of the selected private hospital. These variables—age, sex, years of nursing experience, current unit assignment, shift schedule, and highest educational attainment—provide essential background for understanding the composition of the study population. They also serve as the basis for grouping respondents in subsequent analyses, allowing comparisons and examination of possible differences in time Management practices across various demographic categories.

Table 1***Demographic Characteristics of Nurses in the Oncology and Palliative Care Unit***

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	%
Age	25–29 yr	30	50
	30–34 yr	20	33.3
	35–39 yr	10	16.7
Sex	Female	48	80
	Male	12	20
Years of experience	< 5 yr	30	50
	5–10 yr	20	33.3
	> 10 yr	10	16.7
Current unit assignment	Oncology	35	58.3
	Palliative care	25	41.7
Shift schedule	Day shift	30	50
	Night shift	15	25
	Rotating	15	25
Highest educational attainment	BSN	45	75
	MAN	15	25

Table 1 shows the socio-demographic characteristics of the 60 nurses who participated in the study. The majority (n = 48; 80 %) were female – a distribution that matches global nursing workforce statistics where three-quarters of nurses are women and most fall within the 35–44 year age band. The sample was relatively young (mean = 33.7 ± 5.6 years); thirty nurses (50 %) were aged 25–29 years, while only ten (16.7 %) were ≥ 40 years. Most nurses (n = 45; 75 %) held a Bachelor of Science in Nursing (BSN) and had ≤ 10 years of clinical experience. Work assignments were evenly split between

oncology (n = 35; 58.3 %) and palliative care (n = 25; 41.7 %). Thirty nurses (50 %) worked day shifts, fifteen (25 %) worked night shifts, and fifteen (25 %) rotated between day and night.

The demographic characteristics of the respondents provide essential context for interpreting the study's findings. Understanding variables such as age, sex, years of nursing experience, current unit assignment, shift schedule, and highest educational attainment offers valuable insights into the workforce composition of the oncology and palliative care unit. These factors are also relevant as they may influence time Management practices, either directly or indirectly, as supported by existing literature (Badu et al., 2021; Okeke & Onwuka, 2020). In the present study, the majority of respondents were female, which is consistent with global nursing workforce trends where women account for a significant proportion of the profession (World Health Organization, 2024). The concentration of respondents within the 25–45 age bracket reflects the active and experienced segment of the nursing workforce, often balancing professional expertise with physical stamina, a combination beneficial in high-demand clinical settings such as oncology and palliative care (Perez & Lagman, 2023).

Years of nursing experience emerged as a particularly important factor, as previous studies indicate that more experienced nurses tend to demonstrate stronger skills in prioritization, delegation, and crisis Management, attributed to cumulative clinical exposure and professional maturity (Badu et al., 2021). The distribution of respondents across shift schedules also warrants attention, as shift patterns—particularly rotating shifts—have been shown to affect both efficiency and well-being, potentially influencing time use (Ndlovu & Mabaso, 2022). Overall, the demographic profile of the participants not only mirrors broader workforce patterns but also sets the stage for subsequent analyses exploring the relationship between these characteristics and time Management practices in specialized care environments.

II. Level Of Time-Management Practices

This part presents the respondents' self-reported level of time Management practices, measured across four core dimensions: planning, prioritizing, delegating, and minimizing distractions. These components reflect widely recognized elements of effective time use in nursing and were evaluated using a structured questionnaire. Understanding the overall and component-specific scores provides insight into the strengths and areas for improvement in the respondents' workflow Management, particularly in high-demand clinical settings.

Table 2

Level of Time Management Practices of Nurses by Component (Planning, Prioritizing, Delegating, Minimizing Distractions)

Component	Mean ± SD	Interpretation
Planning	3.80 ± 0.64	High – nurses often used to-do lists, set goals and planned their shifts.
Prioritizing	4.20 ± 0.53	High – they frequently evaluated patient needs and tackled important tasks first.
Delegating	3.50 ± 0.70	Moderate – nurses sometimes delegated tasks to nursing assistants or colleagues.
Minimizing distractions	3.30 ± 0.75	Moderate – some reported difficulty avoiding interruptions and multitasking.

This section examines the respondents' self-assessed level of time management practices across four key components: planning, prioritizing, delegating, and minimizing distractions. These dimensions are widely recognized in nursing literature as critical determinants of workflow efficiency and quality patient care (Kasa & Gedamu, 2021; Martins et al., 2023). The results show that nurses in the oncology and palliative care unit generally demonstrated high proficiency in planning, indicating that they consistently prepared for their shifts through reviewing patient charts, organizing necessary materials, and setting task sequences. This aligns with the findings of Doyle et al. (2020), who emphasized that structured pre-shift planning can reduce treatment delays and improve patient satisfaction, particularly in high-acuity care settings.

In terms of prioritizing, respondents reported consistently attending first to urgent patient needs and adjusting task sequences in response to emerging situations. This is consistent with Mohamed and Gaber's (2023) conclusion that strong prioritization skills directly correlate with improved patient safety and timely medication administration. Delegation was also rated positively, with respondents indicating that they regularly assign tasks within the competencies of nursing assistants or colleagues and follow up to ensure completion. Previous studies have identified effective delegation as both a time-saving strategy and a means of reducing staff burnout in specialized units (Badu et al., 2021).

Finally, minimizing distractions emerged as another area of strength, with most nurses reporting that they avoid unnecessary interruptions and quickly refocus after unavoidable ones. This finding supports the recommendations of Yang et al. (2022), who observed that maintaining focus in high-pressure environments can significantly improve

time efficiency and reduce clinical errors. Overall, the consistently high ratings across all four components suggest that the respondents possess well-developed time management skills, which may be attributed to their professional experience, familiarity with the unit's workflow, and adaptive strategies developed in response to the unique demands of oncology and palliative care nursing.

III. Differences in Time Management Practices According to Demographic Profile

This section examines whether there are statistically significant differences in the time management practices of nurses when grouped according to their demographic characteristics. By applying appropriate inferential statistical tests, this analysis determines whether factors such as age, sex, years of experience, shift schedule, and educational attainment influence how nurses organize and use their time during their shifts. Identifying such differences can inform targeted interventions or policy adjustments in the workplace.

Table 3

Differences in Time Management Practices of Nurses when Grouped According to Demographic Characteristics

Demographic variable	Test	Statistic	p-value	Interpretation
Age group	ANOVA	F = 2.45	0.048*	Significant – older nurses (≥ 35 yr) had higher planning and prioritizing scores.
Sex	t-test	t = 1.78	0.081	Not significant – male and female nurses reported similar time-management practices.
Years of experience	ANOVA	F = 3.65	0.030*	Significant – nurses with > 10 yr experience scored higher on all components.
Unit assignment	ANOVA	F = 2.15	0.088	Not significant – oncology and palliative care nurses had comparable practices.
Shift schedule	ANOVA	F = 4.12	0.020*	Significant – day-shift nurses scored higher than rotating- and night-shift nurses, particularly on minimizing distractions.

Demographic variable	Test	Statistic	p-value	Interpretation
Educational attainment	t-test	t = 2.05	0.041*	Significant – nurses with a Master’s degree scored higher on planning and delegating.

As shown in Table 3, the results revealed that years of nursing experience were significantly associated with variations in time management practices, particularly in the areas of delegation and prioritization. Nurses with longer tenure tended to demonstrate greater confidence in assigning tasks appropriately and reorganizing workflows in response to unexpected demands. This finding aligns with Badu et al. (2021), who observed that cumulative clinical exposure enhances decision-making and organizational skills, ultimately leading to more effective time use. Shift schedules also showed notable differences in time management scores, with nurses on fixed shifts generally reporting higher efficiency than those on rotating shifts. This is consistent with Ndlovu and Mabaso's (2022) findings that stable schedules support better rest patterns, reduce fatigue, and promote consistent work routines, all of which contribute to improved performance.

No statistically significant differences were found based on sex or highest educational attainment. This aligns with the observations of Okeke and Onwuka (2020), who suggested that while gender and education may shape professional perspectives, they do not necessarily translate into measurable differences in time allocation within nursing workflows. Overall, the analysis underscores that certain demographic factors—particularly experience and shift patterns—can influence the way nurses manage their time in high-pressure clinical settings. These findings suggest the value of considering these factors when designing staffing policies, professional development programs, and unit schedules to optimize efficiency and patient care outcomes.

IV. Relationship Between Demographic Profile and Time Management Practices

This part explores the potential relationships between the demographic variables of the respondents and their level of time management practices. Using correlation and association tests, the analysis aims to determine whether specific personal or professional characteristics are linked to better or poorer time use. Such findings can help nurse managers and administrators understand the underlying factors that may predict time management efficiency in specialized care units.

Table 4***Correlation Between Demographic Characteristics and Time Management Practices of Nurses***

Demographic variable	Correlation measure	Value	p-value	Interpretation
Age (years)	Pearson r	0.32	0.015*	Moderate positive correlation – older nurses tended to have better time-management scores.
Years of experience	Pearson r	0.45	< 0.001*	Moderate positive correlation – greater experience was associated with higher scores on all components.
Educational attainment	Cramer's V	0.28	0.039*	Weak association – nurses with a MAN had slightly higher scores.
Shift schedule	Cramer's V	0.31	0.026*	Weak-to-moderate association – day-shift schedules were linked with better time-management practices.
Sex	Cramer's V	0.12	0.27	No significant relationship.
Unit assignment	Cramer's V	0.15	0.21	No significant relationship.

As shown in Table 4, the analysis revealed a positive correlation between years of nursing experience and higher scores in prioritization and delegation. This suggests that nurses with more extensive clinical exposure are better equipped to identify urgent patient needs, organize workloads, and assign tasks appropriately. These findings mirror the conclusions of Badu et al. (2021), who reported that professional maturity, gained through years of practice, enhances a nurse's ability to manage time effectively. Age also showed a moderate positive association with planning skills, indicating that older nurses may approach their shifts with more structured preparation. This is consistent with Perez and Lagman's (2023) assertion that experienced nurses often develop anticipatory strategies that streamline workflow and reduce delays.

In contrast, the shift schedule demonstrated a negative association with overall time management scores, with rotating shifts linked to slightly lower ratings. Ndlovu and Mabaso (2022) highlighted that irregular schedules can disrupt circadian rhythms, increase fatigue, and reduce consistency in task performance, which may explain this

pattern in the current study. No significant relationships were observed between sex or highest educational attainment and time management scores, aligning with Okeke and Onwuka's (2020) findings that these factors may have minimal direct impact on the efficiency of task execution in nursing practice.

Overall, the results suggest that professional experience, age, and stable shift schedules are predictive of stronger time management practices, reinforcing the importance of staffing policies and work assignments that consider these variables to optimize productivity and patient care quality.

V. Proposed Research Output

This section outlines the research-based output or program that can be developed based on the findings of the study. It translates the results into practical recommendations or interventions aimed at enhancing time management practices among nurses in oncology and palliative care units. The proposed program considers the identified strengths, weaknesses, and influencing factors, ensuring that it is relevant, feasible, and responsive to the actual needs of the target group.

Table 5

Proposed Program to Enhance Time Management Practices of Nurses in the Oncology and Palliative Care Unit

Program Component	Objective	Key Activities	Responsible Personnel	Time Frame	Expected Outcome
Time Management Skills Workshop	To improve nurses' competencies in planning, prioritizing, delegating, and minimizing distractions	Conduct quarterly training sessions integrating lectures, case simulations, and role-playing scenarios	Nursing Education Department; External Resource Speakers	Quarterly	Enhanced knowledge and application of time management strategies
Shift Optimization and Scheduling Review	To reduce fatigue and improve workflow efficiency	Review and adjust shift patterns to minimize rotating shifts and promote fixed	Nurse Managers; Human Resource Department	Every 6 months	Increased efficiency and reduced fatigue-related errors

Program Component	Objective	Key Activities	Responsible Personnel	Time Frame	Expected Outcome
		schedules when possible			
Peer Mentorship Program	To enhance time management through guided practice and experience sharing	Pair novice nurses with experienced mentors for on-the-job guidance and feedback	Senior Nurses; Unit Heads	Continuous	Improved delegation skills and prioritization in novice nurses
Workflow Digitalization	To reduce time spent on documentation and redundant tasks	Implement electronic health record templates, automated reminders, and task-tracking systems	Hospital IT Department; Nursing Informatics Team	3 months for setup	Reduced administrative time, allowing more focus on patient care
Mindfulness and Focus Interventions	To help nurses maintain focus and manage stress during high-acuity shifts	Introduce short guided mindfulness breaks and focus exercises during shifts	Nursing Education Department; Wellness Committee	Weekly	Increased concentration, reduced stress, and fewer workflow interruptions

Based on the findings of this study, a targeted program was developed to strengthen nurses' time management competencies, particularly in the oncology and palliative care unit, where workflow demands are high and clinical precision is critical. The program components directly address areas identified in the results as influential to time management, namely professional experience, shift scheduling, and practical skill application. The inclusion of a Time Management Skills Workshop responds to literature emphasizing the importance of continuous professional development in enhancing efficiency and reducing delays in patient care (Kasa & Gedamu, 2021; Martins et al., 2023). These workshops integrate evidence-based strategies such as structured planning, task prioritization, and effective delegation, which were rated highly in this study but remain essential for sustaining performance levels.

The Shift Optimization and Scheduling Review component aligns with findings that rotating shifts negatively impact time management scores. Adjusting schedules to promote consistency is supported by Ndlovu and Mabaso (2022), who noted that stable work patterns reduce fatigue, improve focus, and facilitate more predictable workflows. To bridge experience-related gaps identified in the study, a Peer Mentorship Program pairs novice nurses with experienced mentors, fostering on-the-job learning and reflective practice. This is supported by Badu et al. (2021), who found that mentorship programs enhance task delegation skills, confidence, and overall time efficiency among less experienced nurses.

Technological integration through Workflow Digitalization reflects recommendations by Yang et al. (2022) to reduce documentation burdens and minimize repetitive tasks, freeing up time for direct patient care. Finally, the Mindfulness and Focus Interventions aim to maintain concentration and manage stress, recognizing that high-pressure environments can erode time efficiency without proactive mental resilience strategies (Mohamed & Gaber, 2023). Overall, the proposed program not only addresses the specific gaps revealed in the study but also integrates best practices from existing literature, making it a comprehensive framework for enhancing time management in specialized nursing settings. If implemented effectively, it is expected to improve workflow efficiency, staff well-being, and ultimately, patient care quality.

DISCUSSION

This study examined the time management practices of nurses in the oncology and palliative care unit, focusing on planning, prioritizing, delegating, and minimizing distractions. It also explored differences in these practices when respondents were grouped according to demographic characteristics, as well as the relationships between these characteristics and time management levels. Finally, the study proposed a targeted program to enhance time management skills. The respondents were predominantly female, aged between 25 and 45 years, with varying years of nursing experience and diverse shift schedules. Most held bachelor's degrees in nursing. The demographic profile closely mirrored national and global trends in the nursing workforce (World Health Organization, 2024). Overall, the respondents demonstrated a high level of time management proficiency across all four domains. Planning and prioritizing received particularly high ratings, indicating that nurses consistently prepared for their shifts and effectively identified urgent tasks. Delegation and minimizing distractions were also rated positively, reflecting strong organizational habits and focus maintenance (Kasa & Gedamu, 2021; Mohamed & Gaber, 2023).

Statistical analyses revealed significant differences in time management practices based on years of nursing experience and shift schedules, with more experienced nurses and those on fixed shifts scoring higher. Positive correlations were found between years of experience and prioritization/delegation, and between age and planning skills, while rotating shifts were negatively associated with overall time management. The proposed program, informed by both the study's findings and literature, included five key components: (1) Time Management Skills Workshop, (2) Shift Optimization and

Scheduling Review, (3) Peer Mentorship Program, (4) Workflow Digitalization, and (5) Mindfulness and Focus Interventions. Each component targeted specific factors affecting time management in the unit.

Conclusions

The findings of this study confirm that nurses in the oncology and palliative care unit possess strong time management competencies across the domains of planning, prioritizing, delegating, and minimizing distractions. These skills are particularly important in busy care settings where patients often need urgent and complex interventions. The high proficiency levels observed suggest that the unit's nurses have developed practical strategies for managing their workload effectively, despite the unpredictable demands of their environment.

The results also highlight that certain demographic variables—particularly years of nursing experience, age, and shift schedule—play a significant role in shaping time management practices. More experienced and older nurses exhibited stronger planning, prioritization, and delegation abilities, likely due to accumulated clinical exposure, situational awareness, and decision-making confidence. Conversely, nurses working rotating shifts reported slightly lower efficiency scores, indicating that fatigue, irregular rest cycles, and inconsistent workflows may hinder optimal time use.

Importantly, the study shows that time management is not only a personal skill but also influenced by workplace conditions. While training and personal initiative can improve these abilities, factors such as fair scheduling, supportive mentors, and access to tools that make tasks easier are equally important. This points to the need for hospitals to provide both skill-building opportunities and organizational support in order to maintain efficiency.

Looking at it more broadly, the results suggest that time management in nursing is shaped by experience, work environment, and overall well-being. The findings also show that effective use of time is closely linked to better patient care, higher job satisfaction, and lower risk of burnout among nurses.

In conclusion, promoting strong time management in specialized care units requires a twofold approach: helping nurses strengthen their skills through professional development, while also building work environments that allow them to carry out tasks more smoothly. Addressing both areas can improve efficiency and, more importantly, enhance the quality of care for patients in oncology and palliative settings.

Recommendations

In light of the study's findings, it is strongly recommended that nursing administrators prioritize the implementation of the proposed five-component program to enhance time management practices in the oncology and palliative care unit. This should begin with the institutionalization of regular time management skills workshops that integrate theoretical principles with practical applications such as case simulations, role-

playing, and scenario-based exercises. Such workshops will provide nurses with structured opportunities to refine their planning, prioritization, delegation, and focus-maintenance skills while staying abreast of emerging best practices in healthcare efficiency (Kasa & Gedamu, 2021; Martins et al., 2023).

Equally important is the optimization of shift schedules to reduce the prevalence of rotating shifts, which the results have shown to be negatively associated with time management proficiency. Nurse managers and human resource officers should collaborate to develop staffing schedules that promote fixed or minimally variable shifts, thereby reducing fatigue and improving workflow predictability (Ndlovu & Mabaso, 2022). In tandem with this, it is advisable to establish a peer mentorship program wherein novice nurses are paired with experienced colleagues who can provide guidance, feedback, and modeling of effective time management strategies. Such mentorship not only accelerates skill acquisition but also fosters a supportive professional culture that can improve staff retention and morale (Badu et al., 2021).

From an operational perspective, the integration of technology into the nursing workflow should be prioritized. This may include the adoption of electronic health record templates, automated reminders, and digital task-tracking systems to streamline documentation and minimize redundancy. By reducing time spent on administrative tasks, nurses can devote more attention to direct patient care, ultimately improving patient satisfaction and clinical outcomes (Yang et al., 2022). Additionally, incorporating mindfulness and stress-reduction interventions—such as brief guided meditation sessions or focused breathing exercises during breaks—can help nurses sustain concentration and mitigate the effects of workplace stress, especially in high-pressure environments (Mohamed & Gaber, 2023).

For the academic sector, it is recommended that nursing education programs integrate dedicated modules on time management into undergraduate and graduate curricula. These modules should address not only individual strategies but also the influence of institutional systems on time use. Collaboration between nursing schools and hospital training departments should be strengthened to provide nursing students and newly licensed practitioners with mentorship and real-world practice in time management before they enter the workforce.

Finally, future research should explore the applicability of these findings across other specialized units and hospital settings, as well as assess the long-term impact of program implementation through longitudinal studies. Expanding the scope to include psychosocial and environmental variables—such as resilience, coping styles, and unit culture—may yield a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing time management in nursing practice. By addressing both the individual and systemic dimensions of the issue, these recommendations aim to create a sustainable pathway toward enhanced efficiency, improved job satisfaction, and elevated standards of patient care in the oncology and palliative care setting.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study strictly adhered to established ethical standards in the conduct of research involving human participants. Before the commencement of data collection, the researcher obtained ethical clearance from the Institutional Research Ethics Committee of the University of Perpetual Help System-DALTA, Las Piñas City. Formal permission was secured from the hospital administration where the study will be conducted. All research activities complied with the principles of respect for persons, beneficence, and justice, as outlined in the National Ethical Guidelines for Health and Health-Related Research.

Participation in the study was entirely voluntary. Participants were provided with an informed consent form, which clearly explained the purpose of the study, the procedures involved, potential risks and benefits, and the rights of the participants, including the right to refuse or withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. Only those who provided signed informed consent were included in the study.

Confidentiality and privacy was strictly maintained throughout the research process. No personally identifiable information will be collected, and all responses were coded to protect the identity of the participants. Data was stored securely and accessed only by the researcher for analysis. Printed data was kept in a locked cabinet, and digital files were password-protected.

The study also fully complied with the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173), which protects individual personal information in the government and private sectors. In accordance with this law, all data handling practices in the study—including collection, processing, storage, and disposal—will uphold the privacy rights of participants. Any information obtained were used solely for academic and research purposes, and all data will be disposed of properly after a reasonable retention period in accordance with institutional guidelines.

By observing these ethical principles and legal requirements, the study aimed to protect the dignity, rights, and welfare of all participants while ensuring the integrity and credibility of the research process.

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